

CASE STUDY

Tourist safety and security in the Central Region of Ghana - overview and case study

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Abstract – As a result of the sharp rise in the interest for tourism activities, safety and security matters have also become one of the forces causing vicissitudes in the tourism industry in the world. Since tourism sector is contributing greatly to environmental sustainability, tourist safety is also now critical to tourism growth. In the travel and tour experiences, the satisfaction of a tourist is discussed as part of a tourist's post-procured and consumed assessment of the destination. Review of the three most prominent tourism plans in Ghana was conducted in this study. It was discovered that there was no tourist safety policy and establishment of tourism office in most of the MMDAs. This situation has bred weak governmental administrative linkages and neglect of tourist safety and security at the MMDAs. Three tourist facilities in the Central Region of Ghana were chosen for the review-study. Responses of 550 tourists were reviewed in the study. Chi-square test was used to test whether the feeling of safety at the destination was influenced by their purpose of visit. The lingering thought-provoking question about these visits is, how safe and secured are the tourists and visitors in these facilities? It is recommended that GTA should lead the campaign exercise in these three facilities to produce a digital tourist safety and security documentary about each facility and this can assist and boost the confidence of potential tourists to appraise the safety and security of the destination before traveling.

Keywords – safety, sustainability, tourism, growth, policy, digital

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Introduction

Tourism industry has now become one of the biggest, effective and reliable instruments for economic development mostly in the developing nations. Consequently, it has helped these countries to move away from a dependency on agriculture and manufacturing sectors (Tooman, 1997, UNWTO, 2014). As a result of the sharp rise in the interest for tourism activities, safety and security matters have also become one of the forces causing vicissitudes in the tourism industry in the world. Therefore, the failure or success of a tourist destination depends on being able to offer a safe and secured environment for tourists (Tarlow, 2009, Boakye, 2011).

In a study conducted by CNN on consumers' travel perceptions in 2013 involving respondents from more than seventy countries, 67% of the tourist-respondents rated safety and security of a tourist destination as

more worrying than the cost and reputation of the destination. It means that in spite of the fact that cost is an important factor in choosing a vacation destination, contemporary international travelers now place safety and security first among all considerations. In the opinion of Korstanje (2011), so far as international travel is concerned tourists experience a great deal of anxiety and it is now discovered that perception of risk and safety influence tourists' decision to travel.

On 4th November, 2016 (UNWTO Press Release No.16084) the then Secretary-General, Taleb Rifai declared before few days to the start of UNWTO Minister Summit in London that, safety and security was the cardinal mainstay of tourism growth and that the players must build up common front to construct a safe, secure and seamless travel frame in the industry.

Admittedly, there is no one definition for the term “security” and the terms “security” and “safety” are generally used interchangeably (Tarlow, 2009; Payam, 2015). Safety can be defined as the state or condition of being protected from risk, harm or inconvenient outcome. It can also refer to the control of identified and anticipated dangers in order to achieve an appreciable level of being free from risks. However, security can be defined as a system of preventing and protecting against dangers that threaten a person, a group of persons, an organization or a facility of its purpose of existence. In terms of tourism, tourism security considers reducing the risk of accident, unhappy situation and protecting a tourist and the facility against deliberate harm or assault. Also, safety in terms of tourism can be seen as the protection of tourists from unintended incident and unhappy conditions during their recreational activities in a tourist destination or facility. It must be said that, in the literature, researchers sometimes put the two words into one whole and call it “tourism surety” (Tarlow, 2009).

The Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Index 2017 (TTCI, 2017)

For the past eleven years, “The World Economic Forum” has involved significant industry players through its Aviation & Travel Industry Partner Community to conduct a detailed examination of the Travel and Tourism (T&T) competitiveness of economies in the world. The end product is termed “Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Report” and in 2017 at the core of the report was the seventh edition of the Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Index (TTCI). TTCI covered 136 economies in 2017 and its objective was to provide a comprehensive strategic tool for measuring the set of factors and policies that enable the sustainable development of the travel & tourism sector. TTCI in turn impacts greatly on the development and competitiveness of the countries included in the analysis.

On the TTCI 2017 framework, four index areas are identified, namely: i) enabling environment, ii) T&T policy and enabling conditions, iii) infrastructure and iv) natural and cultural resources. Safety and security fall under enabling environment among other sub-themes in this category and their inclusion supports the observation that, the important constituent of a tourist offer is the safety factor which includes personal safety (Czarnecki, 2012, Cooper et al 2008) of all tourists.

The State of World Travel and Tourism

In 2017, the travel and tourism industry made steady growth path way by driving growth, creating jobs, reducing poverty and promoting development and tolerance. Tourism industry contributed US\$ 7.6 trillion to the global economy amounting to 10.2% of global

GDP and created 292 million jobs in 2016. In the report, it is stated that for every 30 new tourists or arrivals to a tourist destination, one job avenue is generated and this phenomenon has made tourism industry employment generator especially in the developing countries including Ghana.

Table 1: TTCI 2017 Safety and Security Ranking in Africa

Country	Safety & Security Ranking (over 136 countries)	Score over 10.0 marks
Rwanda	9	6.39
Morocco	20	6.14
Mauritius	33	5.88
The Gambia	52	5.63
Zimbabwe	60	5.52
Ghana	62	5.49
Senegal	64	5.45
Lesotho	71	5.41
Zambia	73	5.40
Malawi	74	5.40
Botswana	77	5.34
Gabon	80	5.29
Algeria	81	5.28
Namibia	82	5.24
Benin	83	5.24
Cape Verde	86	5.19
Sierra Leone	90	5.14
Tanzania	92	5.05
Madagascar	93	5.02
Cote d’Ivoire	96	4.97
Ethiopia	99	4.90
Tunisia	102	4.68
Uganda	104	4.61
Mozambique	105	4.57
Cameroon	110	4.25
South Africa	120	3.93
Kenya	129	3.45

Admittedly, the tourism sector is contributing greatly to environmental sustainability. This is because air traffic since 1980’s has doubled every 15 years and resource efficiency, environmental protection and climate change issues have been key matter of concerns among the agenda of travel and tourism industry in the world (TTC Report, 2017). The Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Report 2017 assessment has four key findings from the results and these are:

- In the developing countries and especially in the Asia-Pacific region, travel and tourism competitiveness is improving.

- Travel and tourism industry still builds bridges instead of walls between people and places, hence the manifestation of globalization.
- As part of the fourth industrial revolution, countries are developing their digital strategy resulting in increased connectivity among and between nations in the world.
- Travel and tourism industry is still faced with developing sustainability in spite of the growing awareness of the importance of the natural environment to tourism growth.

In the TTCI Index 2017 report, safety and security plays a significant role in determining the competitiveness of travel and tourism industry in the 136 countries being assessed. Furthermore, it was revealed that tourists would be discouraged from travelling to unsafe countries or destinations. Factors that were considered in safety and security assessment included: how costly common crime and violence were, the extent to which police services were responsive in providing protection for travelers from crime, how freely travelers could move and feel safe at the destination and how freely travelers could use the facilities and attractions at the tourist destination. From Table 1, only two countries in Africa, Rwanda and Morocco scored a little over 6 marks out of 10 marks and ranked 6th and 20th respectively among the 136 countries selected. Only 17 countries including Ghana scored a little over 5 out of 10 marks and Ghana was ranked 62nd out of 136 countries in the world in terms of tourist safety and security. This implied that, Ghana and several other African tourist destination-countries though fairly doing well need to work on their safety and security factors to attract travelers and tourists. From the table above, strangely enough South Africa and Kenya that have very attractive tourist facilities scored very poorly in terms of safety and security, 3.93 and 3.45 respectively and ranked 120 and 129 respectively out of the 136 countries chosen for the study. Hence, the compelling force to research into tourist safety and security in tourist destination in Ghana is now apt.

Tourist satisfaction influence repeat visits to a destination

In the opinion of Oliver (1981), in the travel and tour experiences, the satisfaction of a tourist is discussed as part of a tourist's post-procured and consumed assessment of the destination. Therefore, positive satisfaction will have positive effect on tourist's repurchase decision making (Gotlieb, Grewal, & Brown, 1994). In the plethora of academic literature, it is established that satisfaction of a tourist at a destination is a good prediction pointer of the tourists' repurchasing and revisiting choices (Choi & Chu, 2001; Petrick, 2002, 2004; Tam, 2000) and consequently as observed by Petrick and Backman (2002) tourists who have a positive experience during

the period of one recreational activity will possibly repeat the expedition.

Interestingly, the direct correlation between tourist safety and tourist satisfaction has received little attention in the available literature in tourism. For example, Petrick, (2002, 2004) and Yi, (1990) have done some studies on consumer satisfaction but conspicuously missing is the above correlation factor. Furthermore, the fewer works that did some analysis on the consequences of satisfaction like Anderson & Sullivan, (1993) and Baker and Crompton (2000) that worked on intentions for repeat visit still missed out the direct influence of tourist safety on tourist satisfaction.

It has been discovered also by Soderlund (1998) that an increase in consumer satisfaction does not necessarily lead to the same increase in consumer allegiance to a service or product. Lee et al (2007) in the same vein in their study do not identify a significant relationship between satisfaction and the tourist's revisiting intention to a festival or tourism event. It means that the intensity of the relationship between tourist's satisfaction and repeat visit can change, depending on the service or product being analyzed and depending on other variables that can also affect the formation of an individual's expectations (Lee et al., 2007) but the influence of tourist safety is still a stronger factor in this discussion of tourist satisfaction.

Overview of Tourism Institutions and Development in Ghana

Cultural tourism, historical-heritage tourism, convention and event tourism, beach tourism and eco-tourism have been the major attractions among the tourism development and promotions in Ghana. It is observed that various regimes of governments in Ghana have so far placed emphasis on eco-tourism and historical-heritage tourism especially in the Central Region of Ghana, the tourism hub in the country.

Tourism Institutions

In Ghana, the State Hotels and Tourist Corporation was established to supervise the then emerging tourism industry in 1962. The corporation was split into two separate entities in 1965: the Ghana Tourist Corporation and the State Hotels Corporation.

The National Redemption Council (NRC), the ruling military junta in 1973 issued NRC Decree 224 to split the Ghana Tourist Corporation into two: the Ghana Tourist Control Board (GTCB) and the Ghana Tourist Development Company Limited (GTDC). The GTCB exercised the traditional functions of a national tourism organization. In 1977 the Supreme Military Council Decree 80 amended NRC Decree 224 and established the Ghana Tourist Board (GTB). Its primary functions were:

- to advise the ministry in charge of tourism on policy formulation and planning;
- to regulate and control the tourism industry, including registration, classification, licensing and application of standards for catering, accommodation, tour and travel enterprises;
- to market the country and the administrative regions as tourist destinations to both international and domestic tourists; and
- to conduct research and studies on tourism trends and disseminate these.

In 1987 the functions of GTDC were re-oriented to do more on tourism promotion and the mobilization of investment resources, which included financial and technical assistance for small-scale tourism enterprises. GTB then became the main implementing agency and Ghana Tourist Development Company and the State Hotels Corporation took full charge of the commercial involvement in tourism.

Medium Term Tourism Plan, 1993-95 was established as a single-portfolio ministry in March 1993 and the agencies that fell under the Ministry of Tourism then were: i) Ghana Tourist Board, ii) Ghana Tourist Development Company and ii) Hotel, Catering and Tourism Training Centre (HOTCATT).

The private tourism sector enterprises and practitioners in the Ghanaian tourism industry are identified under the following trade associations: Ghana Hotels Association; Ghana Restaurants Association; Ghana Association of Travel and Tour Agents; Travel Writers Association of Ghana; Ghana Board of Airline Representatives; Car Rentals Association of Ghana; National Drinking Bars Association; Chop Bars Association of Ghana; Africa Travel Association - Ghana Chapter; Association of Tourism Consultants; Skal Club International (Ghana) and Tourism Society of Ghana. The functions of these trade associations are prescribed in the National Tourism Development Plan (1996-2010) among which are: i) providing representation on tourism boards and committees; ii) conducting research and training that is relevant to the private sector enterprises and iii) sponsoring special events and becoming involved in marketing activities. Since 1994 the trade and enterprise associations have come under one umbrella in the name of Ghana Tourism Federation (GHATOF), and this was formed to provide a linkage between its membership and the public sector and also make input into tourism development in Ghana. GHATOF is now actively engaged in the promotion of the tourist trade from all spheres and from legislation to human resource training for its members. GHATOF has now emerged as a lobbyist group for private tourism sector operators in Ghana.

Tourism Development in Ghana

In Ghana the official development of tourism began with the appraisal of Ghana's tourism resources in 1970, a decade and three after independence in 1957 (Obuarn Committee, 1972). The result of the appraisal was to list and categorize all the potential tourism resources for a five- year development plan: 1972-1976 period. Finally, this exercise helped the government to identify tourism investment areas to allow foreign involvement in the tourism industry. As a sequel, a number of significant exercises were carried out on numerous aspects of Ghana's tourist industry between 1972 and 1978. It must be said that, due to financial and local technical constraints most of these exercises were sponsored and conducted by foreign agencies and workers, namely:

- Requirements for a comprehensive tourism development strategy were identified by the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) (Stewart, 1973).
- Identification of effective resource utilisation for tourism development was conducted by the United States International Executive Service Corps (Egan, 1975).
- An assessment and review of tourism planning and development, human and resource requirements for the tourism segment conducted by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (Singh, 1978).

The conclusion was that, Ghana had the potential to develop her nascent tourism industry. However, what Ghana needed was the formulation of all-inclusive national tourism development plan to structure the desired long-term sustainable development. It also emerged that low disposable incomes in Ghana and the West African sub-region limited the opportunities for domestic and African sub-regional international tourism. It thus became obvious that Western Europe and North America would be the probable tourism generating markets for Ghana's fledgling tourism industry.

Ghana's First 15-Year Tourism Development Plan: 1975-1990.

The 15-Year Tourism Development Plan was tailored to direct tourism planning for the period with financial and technical assistance from the Danish Government (Hoff and Overgaard Planning Consultants, 1974). In 1975, international tourist arrivals were projected to increase from 64,000 to 357,000 per year by the end of the plan in 1990. So far as economic benefits were concerned, 36,000 new direct and indirect jobs were to be created and projected annual foreign exchange earnings were estimated at \$58 million. Regrettably, the 15-year plan never saw the light of the day due to the landscape of the volatile political economy at that time and the subsequent decade of political instability in Ghana (Teye, 1988), as well as severe economic

quagmire that was unsuitable for attracting both the investment capital and the projected number of international tourists.

Second 15-year Tourism Development Plan: 1996 - 2010

This plan was prepared with financial support from the UNDP and technical assistance from the WTO (UNDP/WTO, 1995). The plan projected total annual international tourist arrivals to increase from 286,000 in 1995 to 1,062,000 in year 2010. The two main tourist product-components that needed to be developed were eco-tourism resources and heritage tourism resources which were linked to cultural attractions and also to the slave trade in West Africa. The Africans in the Diaspora especially from the United States and the Caribbean were the main target groupings in this objective.

Tourism Development Plan- 2013-2027: Issues of Tourist Safety

In the Ghana Tourism Development Plan 2013-2027, the institutions involved in collecting tourism statistics are clearly enumerated, namely: Ministry of Tourism (MOT), Ghana Tourism Authority (GTA), Ghana Immigration service (GIS), Ghana Statistical Service (GSS), Ghana Museums & Monument Board (GMMB), Forestry Commission of Ghana (FCG),

Bank of Ghana (BOG), Ghana Revenue Authority (GRA) and Ministry of Trade & Industry.

Certainly and conspicuously missing is similar list of institutions and collaborators for maintaining and training the destination workers on safety and security at tourist destinations in Ghana. It is only generally believed that the already known public security services like Ghana Police Service are in charge of tourist safety, which always leads to weak tourist safety linkages at destinations. It is only in the Forestry Commission of Ghana that its Wildlife Division has safety gadgets and personnel who mainly protect tourists on a safari in the parks, for example at Kakum National Park and Mole national Park. As a matter of fact, at the Mole National Park no tourist or group of tourists could go on safari without the company of a guard. From the review of the three tourism plans mentioned above, there is no specific or detailed item about the policy of tourism safety and security and also the collaboration among agencies and training of destination workers on safety and security.

In the Ghana Tourism Development Plan (2013-2027) Report, the most preferred places to visit in Ghana have been Kakum National Park (KNP), Cape Coast Castle, Kumasi Zoo, Elmina Castle and Manhyia Palace. However, Kakum National Park, Cape Coast Castle and Elmina Castle are among the major sites most visited in Ghana both by domestic and international tourists between 2011 and 2016 as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Number of Visits to Major Tourist Sites in Central Region of Ghana

Tourist sites	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Elmina Castle	81, 677	92,463	72,305	58,147	91, 524	139,059
Cape Coast Castle	97, 595	97, 676	98, 445	98, 765	99,788	101,131
Kakum National Park	361, 067	362, 743	363, 755	373, 457	382, 556	452,556

Source: Ghana Tourism Development Plan, 2013-2027; Ghana Museums & Monuments Board, 2016; Kakum National Park, 2016.

From Table 2 above, it is revealed that numbers of visitors to the three above tourist facilities in the Central Region of Ghana have been encouraging and almost every year the visits are almost steady. For Elmina Castle, the increase in the number of visits has been rather steady until the sharp increase from 91,524 in 2015 to 139,059 in 2016. In the case of Cape Coast Castle, there has been an appreciable increase every year in the number of visits from 2011 to 2016. In the case of Kakum National Park, the increase in the number of visits to the facility has been phenomenal and between 2015 and 2016 the increase has been over 60,000 visitors. From the Table 1 discussion, the obvious thought-provoking question about these visits is, how safe and secured are the tourists and visitors in these facilities?

Contribution of Tourism Sector in Ghana

The tourism sector in Ghana has remained as a steady contributor to economic growth and development. According to ISSER (2017), tourism has been a major source of foreign exchange, employment and government revenue in Ghana. In the report of World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), in 2016, travel and tourism generated a total of US\$ 7.6 trillion. The contribution of the tourism sector in 2016 to total employment, both direct and indirect was 5.9%, representing 693,000 jobs. In the assessment of ISSER (2017), tourism arrivals were estimated at 1,322,500 in 2016 representing a 10% increase from 2015 as shown in the Table 3 below. Also, as shown in Table 3, revenue from tourism also went up by approximately 10% from US\$ 2, 275.2 million in 2015 to US\$ 2,

505.5 million in 2016. Tourism gross contribution to GDP too has been a steady significance in Ghana as

shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Tourism Indicators in Ghana: 2009 - 2016

Indicator	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Arrivals ('000)	802.8	931.2	1,080.20	903.30	993.60	1,093.0	1,202.2	1,322.5
Receipts (US\$ million)	1,615.20	1,875.00	2,178.9	1,704.7	1,876.9	2,066.5	2,275.2	2,505.5
Gross Contribution to GDP								
GDP	2012	2013	2014	2015	Tourism is now either the 3rd or 4th foreign exchange earner in Ghana.			
	4.8	4.7	4.7	4.8				

Source: Ghana Tourism Authority (GTA), 2016; Ghana Tourism Development Plan.

A Policy of Decentralization: Deficient in Tourist Safety Policy

Among the National Development Planning Commission (NDPC) guidelines for the preparation of the District's Medium-Term Development Plans, it is the responsibility of the Ghana Tourism Authority (GTA) to have an office at the Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies (MMDAs) to help press home the need for MMDAs' tourism issues. Unfortunately, the absence of such tourism office and officials in most MMDAs make tourism planning and tourist safety issues to be coordinated at a distance from the regional GTA office which breeds weak linkages and neglect of tourist safety and security at the MMDAs. The Tourism Act 2011 stipulates that GTA will have an officer in each district in order to set up an office at or near the District Assembly offices and build up a relationship with the assembly to ensure that tourism development is part of the MMDAs plan. Conspicuously, since this is absent in most MMDAs, consequently tourism development issues, including safety and security, are haphazardly handled in Ghana.

Furthermore, among the themes and objectives proposed in the policy document to drive the work of the Ministry of Tourism, Culture and Creative Art (MTCCA) and its implementing agencies are: security, safety and privacy, to ensure the health, security, safety of all tourists and tourist sites safeguarding against negative side effects of tourism on local communities. However, it must be said that the Tourism Act 817 empowers the tourism sector and establishes GTA, among its regulations empowers the "Minister" of tourism to make regulations covering several areas including health, safety and security of groups like tourists, staff, food and beverage, etc. This can be a wake-up call to the "Minister" to pay particular attention to tourist safety and security issues at the various destinations in Ghana.

Comparison of Tangible Tourist Resources in Africa

In 2012, the UNWTO consultant team's experiences on the tour operator survey and stakeholder interviews and interactions conducted revealed that, many tourist source markets see Africa as a continent-tourist product, not as separate countries and tourist destinations. The main tourism appeals are the game parks, cultures and rest/relaxation sometimes at the end of the tour or sometimes considered as the main tourist product of the holiday supported with travels to natural areas or parks. Comparatively, Ghana is able to compete with cultural tourist resources especially "hospitality", classified as intangibles. Among the five tourist destinations considered in the survey namely, Ghana, Senegal, Gambia, Cameroon, Kenya and Republic of South Africa in terms of culture and tourist tangible resources, Ghana, Senegal and Kenya are strongly compared to others. On the other hand, on the same score, Gambia and Republic of South Africa are less competitive than others. In terms of nature tourist tangible resources, Cameroon is strongly compared to others while the rest of the countries are less competitive to Cameroon. Also, in the area of beach tourist tangibles, Gambia, Kenya and Republic of South Africa are strongly compared to others. It must be added that, Ghana is most advantaged in the area of emotional benefits, that is, sense of safety and freedom to discover and exchange at cultural and lifestyle level and African variety. The most distinctive and attractive aspect of this is the general friendliness and warmth that is given to tourists within Ghana. This situation has probably led to the seemingly less attention paid to establishing and maintaining safety policies and collaborations in the country. One can easily say that, if tourist safety conditions and issues are extensively planned and worked on, it will even increase Ghana's share of tourist arrivals because in the modern world of post September 11- aftermath, tourist safety is now part of sine qua non tourist service attributes.

Popular Tourism Attractions in Ghana Ecological Tourist Resources

Ghana has rich ecology made of vegetation, wildlife and waterfalls. Ghana shares rain forest vegetation cover with other West and Central African countries.

The rain forest spans from the western part of Ghana tapering in extent towards the Ashanti and mid-Volta Regions.

Kakum National Park (KNP) which is 33 km north of Cape Coast is a rain forest national park. KNP has a treetop canopy walkway: seven long bridges and four short bridges and is known to be the first of its kind in Africa though now Rwanda and other African countries have similar facility. The park was established in 1992 ((Forestry Commission, 2005). Some of the species of fauna in KNP are Diana monkey, giant bongo antelope, yellow-backed duiker and African elephant. KNP also has a variety of birds for bird watching activity. It has a large variety of butterflies.

Mole National Park (MNP) is located in the Guinea savannah in the Northern Region and is also Ghana's largest national park. MNP was established in 1971 and has a variety of game. It has Mole Motel which is located right in the park with a swimming pool, bar and restaurant facilities.

The monkey sanctuaries in Ghana are: Boabeng-Fiema in Brong Ahafo Region and Tafo-Atome in Volta Region. There are Coastal wetlands known as Ramsar sites and are wetland reserves of international significance because they provide habitats for large numbers of indigenous and migratory water birds. Kintampo Falls in Brong Ahafo Region, Boti Falls in Eastern Region and Wli Falls in Volta Region are the major waterfall sites in Ghana. There is a popular crocodile pond at Paga, a border town in the Upper East Region. There are botanical gardens at Aburi and Bunso Arboretum both in the Eastern Region. These ecological heritage-resources provide a strong foundation for Ghana's eco-tourism promotion.

Seashore Tourist Resources

Beaches are found in the western part of Ghana's 540 kilometre coastline and it stretches between Accra and Axim. These beaches promote sun-sea-sand recreational activities and holidays in Ghana. Some popular beaches in Ghana are La Palm Royal Beach, Coco Beach, Busua Beach, Bojo Beach, Kokrobite Beach, Coconut Groove Beach Resort all in Accra, Elmina Beach in Central Region and Ankobra Beach in Western Region.

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Elmina Beach in Central Region and Ankobra Beach in Western Region.

Cultural Tourist Resources

Cultural tourist resources consist of the tangible and intangible displays of Ghana's culture and are part of the major tourist resources. These are the indigenous music and dance, folklore, handicraft, cuisine, costumes, artefacts, traditional festivals and the institution of chieftaincy. In Ghana, it is observed that cultural resources are the most equitably distributed in the country because every traditional area or town in Ghana has at least one major festival whose celebration brings citizens together annually. Traditional marriages including wedding and funerals are very active resources that pull onlookers and travellers to admire. Furthermore, Ghanaian hospitality an aspect of culture has been a strong factor among tourism promotion. Admittedly, where hospitality is real, a destination stands to benefit as visitors who experience it assist in promoting that destination through positive word-of-mouth publicity.

Historical Tourist Resources

Historical heritage is composed of the monuments and historical sites in Ghana whose popularity and appeal derive from Ghana's pre-colonial history as well as early contacts with the Europeans. The three designated by UNESCO as World Heritage Monuments, namely, St. George's Castle and St. Jago Fort, both in Elmina and Cape Coast Castle are all found in the Central Region of Ghana, the tourism hub. There are other scattered forts and castles found along Ghana's coastline from Axim to Keta, which have some touristic significance: Osu Castle, formerly known as Kristiansborg, built by the Danes is a monument found in the capital city of Ghana, Accra. Other historical monuments include the 19th Century Kumasi Fort and many other European cemeteries also found in the coastal towns. The olden Slave markets are the towns of Salaga in the Northern Region and Assin Manso in the Central Region.

The Pan-African Historical Festival (PANAFEST) which was established in 1992 is now a vibrant feature in Ghana's historical heritage. PANAFEST is now an international cultural fiesta that showcases Ghana's rich culture exemplified in durbars that are held by the chiefs displaying their stool, regalia, totems, maces, traditional multi-colour-designer flags and dazzling Kente clothes. This biennial festival pulls large numbers of Africans in the Diaspora and from the continent, both as participants and tourists. Interestingly Emancipation Day, which is a commemoration of the end of world slavery and which used to be celebrated separately is now celebrated as part of PANAFEST.

Observation of Challenge in Tourist Safety and Security

Considering the intrinsic vulnerability of tourism and its great contribution to the socio-economic development of many nations including Ghana, it is interesting to note that investigation into safety and security measures at tourist facilities is relatively a new research field and still improving (De Sausmarez, 2004; Ritchie, 2004). It must be added that, safety in

tourism increases people’s propensity to travel and also empowers tourists to maintain their plans and visit destinations they have saved cash to travel to. Major events that had negatively impacted on travel and tourism the past two decades have been issues of concern for both tourism practitioners and policy makers. Table 4 below gives a graphic exhibition of some occurrences in the world that gives credence to the above statement.

Table 4: Some events of unsafe conditions that affect tourist safety and security

Date	Event-description
Sept.11, 2001 (9/11)	Terrorist attacks on World Trade Centre in the USA.
March, 2004	Madrid, time bombing on Madrid commuter rail network, Spain.
December, 2004	Tsunami in the Indian Ocean.
July, 2005	Mass murder on underground trains and a bus in Central London.
December, 2014	A Muslim sheikh took 17 people hostage inside a chocolate café in Sydney; Australia.
June, 2015	A mass shooting at a tourist resort at Port El Kantaoui, north of the coast of Sousse; Tunisia
July, 2016	A Syrian asylum seeker blew himself up with a backpack bomb outside a music festival in Ansbach; Germany.
January, 2016	3 tourists were stabbed at Bella Vista Hotel in Hurghada in Egypt.
January, 2016	Attack that killed 10 German tourists in Istanbul’s Sultanahmet historic district; Turkey.
September, 2016	A man was chased and stabbed in a park in Minto, New South Wales; Australia.
December, 2016	Al Karak Jordan attack at Kerak castle, where series of shootings killed 10 people including a Canadian tourist; Jordan.
May 15, 2018	Armed robbery attack on 3 German tourists in Ballito, KwaZulu-Natal on their way to the King Shaka International Airport.

Source: author’s own construct culled from the internet, 2018.

Figure 1: A Map of Central Region Showing the Study Areas in Ghana.

In Ghana, in July, 2015 an accident occurred at Bunso Canopy Walkway in the Eastern Region leading to the injury of about 20 school children who had gone to have fun in the Bunso Arboretum. In March, 2017 another accident occurred at the Kintampo Water Falls where 17 revelers including students from two institutions were

feared dead while many others sustained various degree of injury when trees fell on them at the site in the Brong Ahafo region of Ghana.

As shown in Figure 1, the three tourist facilities are very close to each other and form a triangular frame of tourist attractions. While the Kakum National Park is found in the rain forest, the Elmina Castle and Cape Coast Castle are found at the coast on the Gulf of Guinea in West Africa. Though the three tourist facilities are located in three different District/Metropolitan Assemblies, they geographically form a triangular tourist destination (TTD) in the Central Region of Ghana.

Brief Description of the Case Study Area Cape Coast Castle in Cape Coast

When the Portuguese settled at the present “Cape Coast” township, they christened the town in Portuguese, “Carbo Corso” meaning “short cape” and in 1555 built a structure to be used purposely for trading. The Portuguese name was later corrupted to ‘Cape Coast’ and this is now the accepted name of the capital town of the Central Region of Ghana. However, the Swedish, led by

Krusenstjerna were the originators of the permanent lodge now known as Cape Coast Castle which was built in 1653 and was named after King Charles X of Sweden, Carlousburg. Occupation of the Dutch began in 1660 but later in 1665, the British convoy led by Captain Holmes occupied the fort in 1665 and by 1700 refurbished it into a castle. During the colonial regime, Cape Coast Castle served as the West African headquarters of the president of the Committee of Merchants, the seat of the then British governor and a school. After the abolishing of the slave trade and attainment of Ghana's independence in 1957, the Castle has been used as a historical museum with a Ghanaian arts and crafts gift shop. The Cape Coast Castle is now the regional headquarters of Ghana Museums and Monuments Board (GMMB). The famous Bond of 1844, signed between the British Colonial masters and the Fante Confederation was signed in the Cape Coast Castle. Cape Coast was the first national capital of then Gold Coast (now Ghana) until 1877 when Accra became the capital city of Ghana.

Elmina Castle in Elmina

Elmina was the first place in Ghana where coastal Ghanaians had the contact with European merchants via barter trade system. In 1471 during the reign of King Afonso V, the Portuguese first reached "Ghana" which was then christened as the Gold Coast. Over five decades earlier, Prince Henry the Navigator sent ships to reconnoiter the African coast and consequently this landed the crew on the Gulf of Guinea. Their reasons for travelling all this way on the ocean were for trading and the discovery of the land endowed with gold ore and ivory trapped the Europeans to stay on the West African coast. Another reason for coming down south was the search for direct trade route to India and Asia because they needed to avoid the Arab merchants. It is also believed that the Portuguese were also looking for opportunities to propagate their Christian religion and so subsequently established a cooperation with Prester John who was known to be the elder of a Christian nation in Africa.

Gradually, the trade between Elmina merchants and Portuguese merchants thrived and there was the need to establish a trading post, hence the construction of a fort to facilitate the trade. All the materials needed for the construction were shipped from Portugal to Elmina and it was built in 1482. The fort became the first pre-fabricated building of European origin to have been planned and executed in Sub-Saharan Africa; it was named St. George Castle and this helped Elmina to achieve a status of a proper city in the then Gold Coast partly because the population of Elmina swelled with traders from other neighbouring towns who wanted to trade with the Portuguese merchants and this finally assumed a West-African monopoly south of the Sahara. The Dutch took over the fort in 1637. Most trade in West Africa focused on the sale of human slaves in the 17th Century and the castle was used as a depot where slaves were captured

and brought in from different towns and parts of Kingdoms in West Africa. These slaves owned by the slave catchers were sold to Portuguese and later to Dutch traders in exchange for goods like textiles, gun powder, liquor and other items. The Dutch later built a new smaller fortress on a nearby hill to protect St. George Castle from inland attacks and this fort was called Fort Coenraadsburg. The British took over the Castle in 1872 from the Dutch. In 1814 the slave trade was abolished in the world and since then the Castle has been used for several purposes in Ghana. In the 1990s the castle was restored and refurbished by various Ghanaian governments and a lot of renovations were undertaken. Elmina Castle has now become a great tourist resource or product in Ghana because it pulls greater number of travelers and tourists. Elmina Castle is a place of pilgrimage for many Africans in the Diaspora searching for their root in Africa. Elmina Castle is currently preserved as a Ghanaian national museum and in 1979 it was designated and classified as a World Heritage Monument under UNESCO.

Kakum National Park in Kakum

Kakum National Park (KNP) is a rain forest park very close to the above two Heritage sites in the Central Region of Ghana. KNP is about 15 km from Cape Coast and Elmina. Ghana has an ecological system of 21 protected areas: 7 national parks, 6 resource reserves, 2 wildlife sanctuaries, 1 strict nature reserve and 5 coastal wetlands. The seven national parks are the following: i) Kakum National Park found in the Central Region, ii) Bia National Park found in the Western Region, iii) Bui National Park located in Brong Ahafo Region, iv) Digya National Park in the Volta Region, v) Kyabobo National Park located in Volta Region, vi) Mole National Park in Northern Region and vii) Nini Suhien National Park located in the Western Region.

The type of vegetation in the park is moist evergreen rainforest with tall hardwood up to 65m in height. Kakum Park is a state-owned protected forest reserve which is jointly managed by the Wildlife Division of the Forestry Commission and the Ghana Heritage Conservation Trust (an NGO). Kakum Forest was named after the River Kakum whose headwaters lie within the park's boundaries. It must be said this park was established at the ingenuity of the local people and not by the State Department of Wildlife who are responsible for wildlife preservation in Ghana (Wellington, 1998).

Discussions and Results of Perceptions of Inbound Tourists on Safety at the Cape Coast Tourist Destination

By the use of sample size of 550, purposive and convenience sampling techniques and questionnaire as a research instrument, the country of origin of tourists who visited the tourist destination area in the Central Region of Ghana during the study period between June and

September 2017 were as follows: the majority, representing 38.9% (214) of the 550 respondents were from the USA. The next group of citizens was made of British (UK) whose number was 150 representing 27.3% of the total respondents. Other tourists representing 53 (9.6%), 38 (6.9%) and 25 (4.5%) of the 550 tourists interviewed also came from Netherlands, Germany and France respectfully among other countries. This may imply that among the inbound tourists visiting this tourist destination area, the Americans dominated the foreign visit to Central Region in Ghana and the reason is obvious; that there is a strong ancestral link between the Afro-Americans and the African continent because of the Castles in the region.

Tourists’ Opinion on Issues that Constitute Tourists’ Safety

The tourists were asked to state their opinions on issues that constituted their safety at the destination while enjoying the facilities and interacting with the natives. As shown in Table 5 below, out of 550 respondents, 473 representing 86.0% of the tourists interviewed stated that the main item that constituted their safety was the provision of safety measures at the attraction sites for instance, CCTV Cameras and alarm systems. Another section of the respondents, 6.5% (36) of the tourists affirmed that provision of health facilities at the attraction sites also constituted safety at the attraction sites. Again, others also indicated that safety of destination workers and hospitality of locals provided safety for them. This was represented by 3.6% (20) and 3.8% (21) of the tourists respectfully. Therefore, one can infer that the major constituent of tourists’ safety at the destinations is the provision of safety measures.

Table 5: Opinion on issues that constitute tourists’ safety at destination

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Provision of safety measures	473	86.0
Provision health facilities	36	6.5
Staff safety	20	3.6
Hospitality / friendship of locals	21	3.8
Total	550	100.0

Source: Field work 2017

Safety /security Facilities found at the Attraction Sites

Majority of the tourists representing 69.1% (380) indicated that the main facility they saw at the attraction site was signs and directions. Also, 102 representing 18.2% of the tourists said they found security guards at the sites. Other facilities found included safe deposit box and alarm systems among others as shown in Table 6 below. In addition, 13 tourists representing 2.4 % listed that they saw some CCTV camera in the facilities. As

observed by the researcher one CCTV camera was only found at the KNP. From Table 6 it is shown that 13 of the tourists representing 2.4% stated that they could not identify any security equipment among the rest others observed in the destination.

Table 6: Security Facilities at the Attraction Sites

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
CCTV Camera	13	2.4
Alarm System	12	2.2
Signs & Directions	380	69.1
Safe Deposit Boxes	30	5.5
Security Guards	102	18.5
None	13	2.4
Total	550	100.0

Influence of Tourists’ Purpose of Visit on Perception about Safety at Attraction Site

As revealed in Table 7, out of 17 tourists who visited the sites for business, 15 said they had positive impression on their safety and security in the destination whereas the remaining 2 feared of not being safe while visiting the destination. In addition, 174 tourists out of the 193 tourists who patronized the sites for educational purpose indicated that they were sure of their safety, whereas the remaining 19 tourists said they were not safe at the destination. The majority of the tourists accounting 233 of the 243 respondents who visited the sites for vacation and holidaying responded that they felt safe and secured at the tourist sites while the remaining 10 tourists said they did not feel safe. Finally, out of 97 tourists whose purpose of visit was to visit Family & Friends (F & F), 88 said they were safe and secured while enjoying their travel and visit at the destination whereas the remaining 9 respondents said otherwise.

Table 7: Cross tabulation of Purpose of visit and perception of safety before traveling to the destination areas

Description		Perception of safety before visiting the destination?		
		Safe	Not safe	Total
Purpose of visit	Business	15	2	17
	Education	174	19	193
	Vacation	233	10	243
	Visit F&F	88	9	97
Total		510	40	550

Source: Field work 2017

Generally, the tourists who participated in the survey were confident in their safety and security so far as motivation for visit was concerned. However, the Chi-square test was used to test whether the feeling of safety at the destination was influenced by their purpose of visit.

Table 8 above shows the results of the Pearson Chi-square testing based on the original hypothesis of the study, that:

H_0 (Null Hypothesis): Tourists purpose of visit does not influence perception of safety at the attraction sites.

H_1 (Alternative Hypothesis): Tourist purpose of visit influences perception of safety at the attraction sites.

Table 8: Chi-square test

Description	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.573 ^a	3	0.087
Likelihood Ratio	6.902	3	0.075
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.934	1	0.334
No of Valid Cases	550		

Source: Field work 2017. *df: degree of freedom; *Asymp. Sig.: asymptotic significance or the p-value of the test; *2-sided means 2 by 2 metrical table; ^a 1 cell (12.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.24.

As shown in Table 8 above, using the Pearson Chi-square, it could be observed that the significance value is 0.087 which is greater than the p-value = 0.05, hence we accept H_0 (Null Hypothesis) and conclude that the tourists' purpose of visit does not influence their perception of safety at the attraction sites in Cape Coast-Elmina-Kakum National Park tourist destination in Ghana. Though tourists' purpose of visit does not affect their opinions on safety and security at the above-named destination, necessary safety infrastructure should be identified and vigorously instituted to boost tourists' confidence and travel.

From historical point of view so far as the literature review is concerned, Ghana's tourism promotion and development plans did not consider the issue of tourist safety and security in their deliberations. It was also observed that, in the three tourist sites visited and surveyed, safety issues were not highly promoted except the tree top canopy walk way which is a special facility at the Kakum National Park. From the destination workers' training exercises, safety is conspicuously not classified among the priorities in their management. So far, there is no joint or collaboration effort with any agency to maintain safety practices. Interestingly, tourist inspection exercises are seemly narrowed to the availability of fire extinguishers, entrance and exit in the facilities. As for tourism safety policy, it is non-existent in Central Region and in Ghana as a whole.

On the basis of the fact that tourists perceived that provision and availability of safety gadgets in the tourist facility constituted tourists' safety, it is recommended that GTA should add the inspection and installation of such safety equipment in their annual routine check in all the tourist and hospitality facilities in the region. The various tourism related bodies in the region like Ghana Tourism Authority (GTA), World Conservation Trust, Road and Safety Commission and Ghana Police Service should be tasked to help maintain safety and security at tourist sites.

Training of the security guards should be regular and standard with recognized state security as a permanent supervisory-trainer. From the literature reviewed and observation made at the destination, it would be highly useful if GTA can lead the campaign exercise in these three facilities to produce a digital tourist safety and security documentary about each facility. Application of such digital technologies promoted in the social media in tourism promotion will help instill confidence and surety in the preparation and choice of destinations of potential tourists. Tourists' satisfaction is complete and memorable when the digital tourist safety documentary is confirmed by the experiences at the destination by the tourists. This can even engender repeat visit and promote more visits by new tourists by word of mouth.

In conclusion, since Ghana has for a long period maintained a peaceful political, tourism and social ambience in the West African sub-region and for the fact that tourism is now classified as either the third or fourth foreign exchange earner in Ghana, international standards in developing and maintaining tourism facilities should be strictly adhered to. National, regional, local and private tourism agencies should be meaningfully coordinated and supported to work for common good. In the drafting of local tourism planning and development in Ghana, the inputs and impressions of tourists about tourist safety and security should be incorporated. Once it is revealed that tourists' purpose of visiting the destination does not influence tourists' perception of safety at the attraction sites, the tourism agencies, tour operators and tourism related ventures should take the advantage to provide and promote other tourism structures for improving the life cycle of tourism products and activities in the region.

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